

Statement concerning legal capacity of Joseph Biden and members of his administration.

Based on scientifically proven evidences I declare Joseph Biden mentally ill, and prematurely terminate his presidency due to his incapacity caused by illness, diagnosed as [schizophrenia](#).

Furthermore, I declare all members of his administration, namely, Kamala Harris, Antony Blinken, Janet Yellen, Lloyd Austin, Merrick Garland, Debra Haaland, Tom Vilsack, Gina Raimondo, Marty Walsh, Xavier Becerra, Marcia Fudge, Pete Buttigieg, Jennifer Granholm, Miguel Cardona, Denis McDonough, Alejandro Mayorkas, Michael Regan, Avril Haines, Katherine Tai, Linda Thomas-Greenfield, Cecilia Rouse, Isabel Guzman, Eric Lander, Ron Klain to be mentally ill, and prematurely terminate their offices due to incapacity caused by the same illness.

Following symptoms of schizophrenia are present in every above mentioned case: disturbances of association and affectivity (such as pathological indifference), the predilection for fantasy as against reality, and the inclination to divorce oneself from reality (autism). [While repeatedly urged to act in a right and proper way](#), all of them remain indifferent and manifest all kind of catatonic stupor: negativism, thoughtlessness in consequence of mental block, abulia. Instead of recognition of obvious facts they exercise oneself in tangentiality. i.e. Ganser syndrome. Instead of logical thinking they seems to be driven by compulsion and delusional ideas, such as democratic fundamentalism that is a manifestation of egomania; misconception of self and everything else that results in overestimation of their own capabilities and in improper behavior; monetary idolatry and a great deal other idolatries etc. Erroneous premises are continuously produced in said cases due to repression of unwanted thoughts, misbelief and [lack of true knowledge](#), and these erroneous premises support the further development of a delusional system.

Joseph Biden has an inveterate and incurable senility which is apparent for everyone. But in addition, he is out of control about what he says, so that misspeaks and fallacies appears in his speeches frequently. [In his last speech at the National Constitution Center on 13 July](#), he said incoherently, that the Big Lie is just a big lie. That is really true: all he says is the Big Lie, and entire „American experiment“ is one big lie executed on the entire population. Contrary to what he says, his presidency is not a salvation but rather a farewell that makes evident the definite end of sanity and emergence of boundless democratic self-destruction. It is a ceremonial suicide of the United States of America, just a suicide due to senile decay and without any hope of resurrection.

All other appointments, orders, and acts, made, enabled, performed or signed by Joseph Biden are therefore invalid. Kamala Harris appointed him as vice president is likewise incapable of contracting, not only because she was insane [at the time I applied to her colleagues](#), but also due to her obvious incompetence in everything with exception of her megalomania. The Biden-Harris administration consists of lobbyists, schizophrenic feminists, and self-interested plotters, many of them at the age of Joseph Biden. Together they do exactly that what Gustave Le Bon describes in

his book „The Psychology of the Crowd“: „inevitable financial waste, and ... the progressive restriction of the liberty of the individual.“ But instead of insight they exercise themselves in self-righteousness, relentlessness and madness, squander resources, and drive entire world into disaster.

The reality behind democratic storefront is quite different: ailing economy, ill population, ruined education, illegal consolidation of institutional powers, corrupt and mad elite, reckless stupidity of the military-industrial complex, and that enumeration may be continued. But „they are sightless guides leading other sightless people, and if sightless people guide other sightless people, they will fall into some pit.“ In spite of that, or exactly because of that, all of them shout „We are people!“ You are not people, but just ignorant and arrogant crowd, incorrigible liars and **obscurants**, as it is written: "God gave them a spirit of stupor, eyes that could not see and ears that could not hear, to this very day.“

This conclusion they confirm every day with their deeds and words. Characteristic in this respect is **the speech of Joseph Biden during his meeting with Angela Merkel on 15 July**, I cite: „Both our nations — both our nations understand the imperative of proving that democracies can deliver the needs of our people in the second quarter of the 21st century. We will stand up for democratic principles and universal rights when we see China or any other country working to undermine free and open societies.“

In his speech far away from the reality behind democratic storefront Joseph Biden presents him as an aged Goebbels while his „dear friend“ is a personification of Hitler. Actually, both ignore their dementia, incapacity, and crimes committed in the past (like involvement of Joseph Biden in mass incarceration of blacks) and continued in the present. **But if Germans come together, their illness only multiplies.** These two are two aged monsters not knowing their own monstrosity because they can not accept such unpleasant notion. Actually, a great deal of peoples who praise both Joseph Biden and Angela Merkel for their alleged achievements are of the same sort as their idols: „**The rest of the people who survived these plagues did not repent from their evil deeds or stop worshiping demons and idols made of gold, silver, bronze, stone, and wood, which cannot see, hear, or walk. They did not repent from their murders, their sorceries, their whoring, or their thefts.**“

Black Attorney General standing behind white policymaker symbolizes reality behind proclaimed unity. The real United States of America consist of forcibly united states, but not of united people. There is no united society, no united interests, no united economy, and nothing united. They all shout „We are people!“, swearing on the Bible, but they all rejected **the Way and the Truth and the Life**, or better to say, the ONLY Way and the ONLY Truth and the ONLY Life that make sense.

It really makes no sense to cite all reliable sources that allow me to state with absolute certainty what I state, because it is not simply the quantity that is decisive. In some cases, one gesture or

word is sufficient to give me such certainty. I do not want to be too longwinded, and therefore, in conclusion of my statement, I assert my truthfulness, and TESTIFY that it is true.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Andrej Poleev". The signature is written in a cursive, slightly slanted style.

Dr. Andrej Poleev
Berlin, 18.07.2021.